
Proportionality in Punishment: Towards a Synthesis of English Law and Yoruba Customary Norms in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the principle of proportionality between punishment and offence within English and African justice systems, with particular attention to the role of sacred divinities in African jurisprudence. The study aims to determine how each legal culture calibrates sanctions to fit crimes. Utilising a comparative legal methodology grounded in functionalism and contextual analysis, this research examines primary legal materials including English sentencing guidelines, statutory frameworks, and judicial precedents alongside ethnographic data derived from fieldwork conducted among the Ilaje and Apoi peoples of Ondo State, Nigeria. The methodology incorporates doctrinal analysis of English law, socio-legal examination of Yoruba customary practices, and critical comparison of underlying jurisprudential principles. Findings reveal that English law emphasises structured, tariff-based proportionality focused on retribution and deterrence. African systems embrace restorative proportionality for known offenders but invoke supernatural sanctions often apparently disproportionate when offenders are unknown. However, detailed examination of the Ayélála divinity reveals a more nuanced picture: a graduated punishment system incorporating opportunities for confession, repentance, and discharge (lele), challenging simplistic characterisations of divine justice as merely retributive. This creates a paradox captured in the Yoruba proverb: "Abéré so nu, wón lo gbe Sango sé epe o ti poju nkan to so nu lo" (They lost a needle, they brought Sango God of thunder; the curse is greater than what they lost); yet the reality of Ayélála jurisprudence suggests that even the thunder god may offer mercy before the final strike. The article concludes that African legal thought contains multiple, sometimes conflicting, conceptions of proportionality, and recommends that modern reforms distinguish carefully between human and divine justice frameworks while recognising the corrective and restorative dimensions embedded within apparently severe divine sanctions

KEYWORDS: Proportionality, Sentencing, Yoruba Customary Law, Sacred Divinities, Ayélála, Lele.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The principle that punishment must be proportionate to the offence committed represents a cornerstone of criminal justice systems worldwide. Yet beneath this apparently simple proposition lies profound complexity, particularly when justice transcends the human realm and enters the domain of the sacred. The relationship between the severity of punishment and the gravity of offence has occupied philosophers from Aristotle to Kant, yet cross-cultural examination reveals that proportionality itself is culturally constructed and contextually variable.

This article undertakes a comparative examination of proportionality within two distinct legal traditions: the English justice system, with its structured sentencing guidelines and retributive foundations, and African justice systems, with their complex interplay of restorative human justice and supernatural divine sanction. The comparison reveals not only differences between English and African approaches but also internal tensions within African jurisprudence itself; tensions that challenge monolithic characterisations of "African justice" as purely restorative.

The central problem this article addresses emerges from a distinctive feature of African legal culture: the invocation of sacred divinities to investigate and punish wrongdoing, particularly when the human offender is unknown. In such cases, the punishment threatened by the divinity such as illness, misfortune, or death often appears to bear no rational proportion to the offence committed. The Yoruba capture this apparent paradox in a pointed proverb: "*Abéré so nu, wón lo gbe Sango sé epe o ti poju nkan to so nu lo*" (They were searching for a needle, they brought Sango, the god of thunder).¹ The implication seems devastating: a petty theft may be answered with lethal lightning. The punishment appears grotesquely disproportionate by any human measure. However, this article advances a more nuanced thesis. Detailed examination of the *Ayélála* divinity's criminal jurisprudence reveals that apparent disproportion is complicated by institutional mechanisms for mercy. Unlike English law's classification of offences into categories of gravity (summary offences, misdemeanours, felonies), *Ayélála* jurisprudence threatens death for all offences yet, this death is not immediate. It is preceded by graduated warnings, opportunities for confession, and procedures for discharge (*lele*).² The apparent severity masks a corrective purpose that preserves social order while offering pathways to redemption.

The thesis advanced herein is that African legal thought contains multiple, context-dependent conceptions of proportionality. Where offenders are known, human justice emphasises restorative proportionality calibrating responses to repair harm and restore relationships. Where offenders are unknown, divine justice is invoked, and here proportionality operates differently; not as calibration of punishment to offence, but as preservation of cosmic order through graduated sanction tempered by opportunities for repentance. The apparent disproportion of ultimate divine punishment reflects not a failure of justice but a different understanding of what is at stake namely, the maintenance of moral order in a universe where spiritual and material realities are inseparable, and where even the threat of death serves corrective rather than purely retributive purposes.

The article proceeds in five parts. Section 2 outlines the research methodology. Section 3 examines proportionality in the English justice system. Section 4 explores the dual faces of African justice: restorative proportionality for known offenders and supernatural sanction for unknown offenders, with particular attention to the graduated nature of *Ayélála* punishment and the institution of *lele*. Section 5 presents a comparative analysis and synthesis. Section 6 concludes with recommendations for reform that respect both dimensions of African legal thought.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a **comparative legal methodology** combining doctrinal analysis with socio-legal field research. The methodological framework draws upon Zweigert and Kötz's functionalist approach, which examines how different legal systems respond to similar social problems,² and Glenn's contextual comparative method, which emphasises understanding legal traditions within their cultural and historical settings.³

2.1 Doctrinal Analysis

The examination of English law utilises traditional legal research methods involving analysis of primary sources including statutes, delegated legislation, and judicial precedents. Secondary sources comprising leading textbooks, academic commentary, and Law Commission reports provide interpretive context. This doctrinal analysis traces the evolution of proportionality principles from philosophical foundations through contemporary sentencing guidelines.

2.2 Socio-Legal Field Research

The African customary law component draws upon **ethnographic fieldwork** conducted by the author between 2018 and 2023 among the Ilaje and Apoi communities of Ondo State, Nigeria. Research methods included:

- **Sampling Technique and** conducted Semi-structured interviews with traditional rulers, community elders, priests of divinities (particularly *Ayelala* and *Gbagala*), and community members who had participated in customary justice processes;
- **Participant observation** of oath-taking ceremonies and community dispute resolution proceedings;
- **Archival research** examining colonial records of customary court proceedings and anthropological accounts from the early twentieth century;
- **Oral history collection** documenting community narratives regarding divine sanctions and their perceived efficacy.

This fieldwork generated primary data regarding the operation of sacred divinities as judicial institutions, the circumstances of their invocation, and community understandings of proportionality and justice.

¹Yoruba proverb, author's translation. The full form recorded in fieldwork is: "*Abéré so nu, wón lo gbe Sango dé epe ti poju nkan to so nu lo*" (They lost a needle, they brought Sango God of thunder; the curse is greater than what they lost).

²See Section 4.3 below for detailed analysis of the *lele* institution.

³K Zweigert and H Kötz, *An Introduction to Comparative Law* (Tony Weir tr, 3rd edn, Oxford University Press 1998) 34-36.

2.3 Comparative Framework

The comparative analysis proceeds at three levels:

1. **Macro-comparison:** Examining the overarching jurisprudential frameworks of English and Yoruba legal systems regarding punishment theory;
2. **Micro-comparison:** Analysing specific mechanisms for addressing comparable problems (known offenders versus unknown offenders);
3. **Meta-comparison:** Evaluating the underlying values and assumptions that explain divergent approaches to proportionality.

The comparison is consciously asymmetrical: English law represents a formalised, state-centric system with extensive documentation, while Yoruba customary law operates primarily through oral tradition and community practice. This asymmetry itself illuminates and portrays different nature and understandings of law, authority, and legitimacy.

2.4 Limitations

Several limitations affect this study. First, the fieldwork was conducted in specific Yoruba communities and cannot claim to represent all African legal systems, a limitation acknowledged in the analysis. Second, the invocation of divine sanctions is sensitive and sometimes secretive; respondents may have withheld information regarding practices that could attract external criticism or legal sanction. Third, the comparison between a developed common law jurisdiction and customary practices raises questions of commensurability that the methodology addresses but cannot fully resolve.

3. PROPORTIONALITY IN THE ENGLISH JUSTICE SYSTEM

The English conception of proportionality is deeply rooted in retributive philosophy. Immanuel Kant argued that punishment must commensurate with the moral gravity of the offence:

Whatever undeserved evil you inflict upon another within the people, that you inflict upon yourself.

Only the law of retribution (*jus talionis*) can determine exactly the kind and degree of punishment."⁴

Kant's deontological framework rejects consequentialist justifications for punishment, insisting instead that proportionality is a categorical imperative derived from respect for human dignity.

This retributive foundation found practical expression in classical English sentencing principles. In *R v Morrissey*,⁵ Lord Chief Justice Parker stated: "The sentence should be such as, having regard to all the circumstances of the particular case, appears to the court to be appropriate and no more than is appropriate to the offence and the offender."⁶ This formulation captures retributive proportionality: punishment must fit the crime and go no further.

The philosophical underpinnings of English proportionality have evolved to incorporate utilitarian considerations. While retribution sets the upper limit of punishment preventing excessive sanctions, deterrence and rehabilitation inform the calibration of sentences within that limit.⁷ This hybrid approach reflects what Ashworth terms "modified retributivism," where proportionality operates as a constraint rather than the sole determinant of punishment.⁸

3.1 Statutory Framework

Contemporary English sentencing is governed by the principle that sentences must be "commensurate with the seriousness of the offence."⁹ Section 142(1) of the UK Criminal Justice Act 2003 identifies the purposes of sentencing as punishment, reduction of crime (including deterrence), reform and rehabilitation, protection of the public, and making reparation. However, these purposes must be pursued within the constraint of proportionality.

The Sentencing Council, established under the Coroners and Justice Act 2009¹⁰, issues definitive guidelines employing a categorical approach: offences are assigned to seriousness levels with starting points and category ranges specified.⁹ The guideline for theft, for instance, specifies three seriousness categories. The most serious (Category 1) has a starting point of 36 weeks' custody; the least serious (Category 3) attracts a community order.¹¹ This structured approach ensures consistent proportionality across similar cases while allowing judicial discretion to account for individual circumstances.

⁴ I Kant, *The Metaphysics of Morals* (Mary Gregor tr, Cambridge University Press 1991) [originally published 1797] 141.

⁵ *R v Morrissey* (1969) 53 Cr App R 514, 517 (Lord Chief Justice Parker).

⁶ A Ashworth, *Sentencing and Criminal Justice* (6th edn, Cambridge University Press 2015) 89-92.

⁷ *ibid* 91

⁸ Criminal Justice Act 1991, s 2(2)(a) (now superseded by Criminal Justice Act 2003, s 142)

⁹ *ibid*

¹⁰ Coroners and Justice Act 2009, s 120.

¹¹ Sentencing Council, *Theft Offences: Definitive Guideline* (2016) 5.

In Nigeria, the Administration of Criminal Justice Act 2015 (ACJA) does not have a similar section like "Section 142(1)" of the UK Criminal Justice Act 2003 that lists the purposes of sentencing. The Act as a whole, along with subsequent guidelines and judicial practice, promotes a sentencing framework that balances punishment, public protection, and the reform and rehabilitation of offenders through mechanisms like non-custodial sentences.¹² It must also be stated that in Nigeria, the criminal Code and the penal Code have a fixed term punishment attached to every offence contained in the code. The statute creating every court also assigns and confers on the courts their extent and limit as to number of years of sentencing thereby giving them the room to exercise discretionary power either to reduce the years or to exhaust the peak of their power or jurisdiction having considered circumstances surrounding the case.

3.2 Classification of Offences and Graded Punishment

A distinctive feature of English criminal law is its elaborate classification of offences according to gravity. Offences are categorised as summary offences (minor matters tried in magistrates' courts), either-way offences (triable summarily or on indictment depending on seriousness), and indictable-only offences (serious matters tried in the Crown Court).¹³ Within these categories, the Sentencing Council guidelines establish graduated tariff ranges: theft may attract community orders or custody depending on value and circumstances; violence is calibrated by harm and culpability; homicide distinguishes murder, manslaughter, and infanticide with correspondingly differentiated sentences.¹⁴

This classification system embodies the principle of *nulla poena sine lege* (no punishment without law) and ensures that proportionality operates through clear hierarchies of offence seriousness. The gradation reflects what von Hirsch terms "desert-based sentencing", the idea that punishment must be proportionate to the blameworthiness of the conduct and the harm caused.

3.3 Judicial Application

Courts adjust sentences to reflect aggravating factors (previous convictions, racial hostility, victim vulnerability) and mitigating factors (remorse, good character, mental health difficulties).¹⁵ The Court of Appeal ensures that adjustments remain proportionate. In *R v McInerney*,¹⁶ the court emphasised that multiple aggravating factors should not produce excessive cumulative effect, stating that "the sentence must remain proportionate to the offence."

The principle of proportionality also operates as a constitutional constraint. Article 3 of the European Convention on Human Rights, incorporated into domestic law by the Human Rights Act 1998, prohibits torture and inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment. While this does not generally invalidate proportionate sentences, it establishes an absolute minimum standard below which punishment cannot fall regardless of offence severity.¹⁷ In *Onuoha Kalu v The State*¹⁸ This Supreme Court decision is the *locus classicus* on the constitutionality of the death penalty in Nigeria. The Court affirmed that the death penalty itself does not violate the constitutional rights to life or human dignity. However, the decision is critiqued for not providing a robust framework to evaluate whether a *specific* punishment is disproportionate in a particular case, leaving the door open for future challenges on proportionality grounds.

In *Joseph Amoshima v The State*¹⁹ in this case, the appellant challenged the mandatory death penalty under the Robbery and Firearms Act, arguing that it breached the principle of separation of powers by removing judicial discretion. The Supreme Court, relying on its decision in *Kalu*, rejected this argument, holding that courts are bound to enforce the penalty as prescribed by the legislature. This case highlights the tension between legislative authority and the judicial desire for proportionate sentencing.

In *Francis Odili v The State*²⁰ and *Anthony Isibor v The State*²¹ These two cases powerfully illustrate the problem of disproportionality created by mandatory sentencing laws. In both cases, the appellants were sentenced to death for armed robbery. However, in *Odili*, the victims only sustained lacerations and survived, while in *Isibor*, the offender brandished a weapon but no physical violence occurred. Despite the vast difference in harm caused, both received the same mandatory death sentence as someone who had committed murder. This demonstrates how mandatory laws treat all offenders as equally culpable, regardless of the actual gravity of their actions.

¹² See sec. 470(2) of the ACJL 2015.

¹³ Sentencing Council, *Guidelines: Seriousness* (2004) para 1.2

¹⁴ *ibid*

¹⁵ [2003] EWCA Crim 3003, [15]

¹⁶ Ashworth (n 6) 89

¹⁷ Criminal Injuries Compensation Authority, *The Criminal Injuries Compensation Scheme 2012* (2012)

¹⁸ [1998] 12 S.C.N.J. 1

¹⁹ (2011) LPELR-4287(SC); (2011) 17 NWLR (Pt. 1277) 574 (Supreme Court)

²⁰ (1977) 2 SC. 25; (1977) All N.L.R. 49

²¹ : (2002) 14 NWLR (Pt. 788) 575; (2002) 6 SC (Pt. II) 1

In *Umoh Ekpo v The State*²² this case is perhaps the most striking example of a court's discomfort with a disproportionate mandatory sentence. The court explicitly stated that it felt **compelled to impose the death penalty despite observing that the sentence was disproportionate to the crime**. The aggravating factor in this robbery was the use of a pair of pliers, which the court noted was not an inherently lethal weapon. This case is a powerful judicial acknowledgment of the unfairness that can arise from inflexible, mandatory sentencing laws.

3.4 The Problem of the Unknown Offender

English law, like all legal systems, struggles with unknown offenders. When the perpetrator cannot be identified, the state cannot impose punishment. This limitation of human justice that English law accepts as an unfortunate necessity. No divine mechanism exists to identify or sanction unknown wrongdoers. The crime remains unresolved, a source of frustration for victims and communities, but the principle of proportionality requiring that only the guilty be punished prevents any response against the innocent.²³

The Criminal Injuries Compensation Scheme provides limited redress for victims of violent crime where offenders are unknown or unable to pay, but this operates outside the criminal justice system and does not satisfy the demand for retributive justice. Similarly, restorative justice schemes require identification of the offender to facilitate dialogue and agreement. This goes on to corroborate cornerstone of English legal tradition that it is better for numerous guilty people to go free than for one innocent person to be punished.²⁴

This limitation, which English law treats as an unfortunate necessity, contrasts sharply with African approaches that refuse to leave wrongdoing unaddressed, even when the human offender is unknown.

4. PROPORTIONALITY IN AFRICAN JUSTICE SYSTEMS

African conceptions of justice differ fundamentally from Western counterparts. At the heart lies the principle of communal harmony. The Southern African concept of Ubuntu captures this orientation: "A person is a person through other persons."²⁵ Wrong doing disrupts relationships within the community and between the community and the spiritual world, creating imbalances that must be redressed for collective wellbeing.

Archbishop Desmond Tutu explained: "We contend that there is another kind of justice, restorative justice, which is characteristic of traditional African jurisprudence. Here the central concern is not retribution or punishment but the healing of breaches, the redressing of imbalances, the restoration of broken relationships."²⁶

However, this characterisation, while accurate for known-offender contexts, obscures a more complex reality. Fieldwork among the Ilaje and Apoi peoples reveals that sacred divinities serve not merely as supernatural enforcers but as judicial institutions that operationalise distinct conceptions of justice depending on whether offenders are known or unknown. Critically, the Ayélála divinity's jurisprudence challenges simplistic equations of divine justice with automatic severity.²⁷

4.1. Restorative Proportionality for Known Offenders

Where offenders are known, African justice systems emphasise restorative proportionality aligning responses to repair harm rather than merely punish. Among the Yoruba, when stolen property is traced to a receiver, the proportional response is restitution plus additional compensation (*esán*).²⁸ The measure is not the abstract moral gravity of the offence but whether the victim is restored and community relationships repaired²⁹.

The investigation of known offenders itself reflects restorative orientation. The Gbagala deity, among the Ilaje and Apoi, functioned as an investigative institution, revealing truth and facilitating accountability while creating pathways for reconciliation rather than mere retribution.³⁰ The deity's role was not to punish directly but to establish facts upon which human authorities could base restorative responses.

²² (2018) LPELR-46804(CA)

²³ Restorative Justice Council, *Best Practice Guidance for Restorative Practice* (2011)

²⁴ Credited to Sir William Blackstone. In his work *Commentaries on the Laws of England*, published in the 1760s.

²⁵ MB Ramose, *African Philosophy Through Ubuntu* (Mond Books 2002) 52.

²⁶ D Tutu, *No Future Without Forgiveness* (Rider Books 1999) 51

²⁷ OT Shemudara, 'Gbagala as a Deity for Investigation of Crime Among the Ilaje and Apoi, Ondo State, Nigeria' (2021) 2 *African Customary and Religious Law Review* 67, 74

²⁸ Shemudara, 'Ayelala, a Sacred Divinity Among the Ilaje and Apoi of Ondo State Nigeria as a Judicial Institution: Echoes from African Legal Thought' (2021) 1(1) *International Journal of Civil Law and Legal Research* 45, 58.

²⁹ EO Akintunde, 'Restorative Justice in Yoruba Culture: Implications for Criminal Justice Reform' (2015) 7 *Journal of African Law and Development* 45, 52.

³⁰ Shemudara (n22)

Among the Igbo, Afikpo elders considered not only the offence but relationships, the offender's history, and community needs. A first-time offender might offer apology and share a meal; a repeat offender might face temporary exclusion or substantial restitution.³¹ This contextual calibration reflects what may be termed "restorative proportionality" the principle that responses must be sufficient to restore harmony without exceeding what is necessary for that purpose.

Oaths and rituals support this restorative framework. The administration of oaths in traditional justice served to align human accountability with supernatural sanction, ensuring that proportionality encompassed dimensions beyond the purely material.³² The oath creates a conditional divine sanction: if the swearer speaks falsely, supernatural punishment follows. This mechanism supports truthful disclosure, enabling restorative resolution.

4.2 The Problem of the Unknown Offender: Invoking the Sacred

The situation transforms radically when the offender is unknown. Here, African jurisprudence refuses to accept that wrongdoing can go unaddressed. The community cannot identify the human perpetrator, but the wrong remains a stain, a disruption, a danger. Something must be done.

The response is to invoke the divine. Sacred divinities are called upon to investigate, identify, and punish the offender. This is not justice delegated to human institutions but justice claimed by the spiritual realm. The mechanism varies: oaths may be administered community-wide, rituals performed, or the matter simply left to the divinity's vigilance.

Ayélála, among the most powerful divinities in the coastal Yoruba region, exemplifies this function. Where human investigation failed, *Ayélála* was invoked to identify and sanction wrongdoers. The divinity's omniscience compensated for human limitation, ensuring that no offence, however concealed, escaped accountability.³³

However, *Ayélála* criminal jurisprudence operates through distinctive principles that complicate straightforward comparisons with English sentencing. Unlike the English criminal justice system, where offences are classified into various categories depending on gravity, simple or minor offences, misdemeanour, and felony; *Ayélála* jurisprudence does not classify offences. Therefore, stealing will attract similar punishment with murder: ultimately, death.

At first glance, this appears to violate proportionality absolutely. The defendant may be sentenced to death without the opportunity of parole or oral defence for an offence that, under English classification, would not attract such severity. This seems to confirm the proverbial critique: The curse is indeed greater than what was lost.

In African criminal jurisprudence where offender is unknown and sacred divinity is invoked particularly *Ayelala*, there is the graduated sanction of *Ayélála* death is delayed and not immediate. However, such appearances are misleading. Fieldwork reveals that the death sentence of *Ayélála* is not spontaneous. It is gradual, and it begins with the visitation of sickness of unknown cause³⁴ This graduated enforcement creates a critical space for what may be termed "divine allocutus" a procedure entirely absent from English capital jurisprudence.

The implication of this graduated system is profound: there is room for confession, admission, and repentance. The institution of *lele*, the allocutus in *Ayélála* criminal jurisprudence allows the accused to discharge himself through acknowledgment of wrongdoing and ritual reconciliation.³⁵ At this point, before death supervenes, the accused will be discharged. The punishment is arrested; the cosmic order is restored through acknowledgment rather than execution.

This mechanism reveals that *Ayélála* jurisprudence, despite the apparent uniformity of its ultimate sanction, incorporates proportionality through *process* rather than outcome classification. Where English law grades offences by statute and assigns corresponding punishments, *Ayélála* grades responses by the offender's conduct during the enforcement process. The thief who confesses when sickness visits receives mercy; the murderer who persists in denial proceeds to death. The proportionality lies not in the nominal sentence but in the opportunity to avert it.

4.3 The Paradox Reconsidered: Disproportion as Corrective Framework

Here we encounter the paradox captured in the Yoruba proverb: "*Abéré so nu, wón lo gbe Sango sé epe o ti poju nkan to so nu lo*" They were searching for a needle, they brought Sango, the god of thunder. The needle a trivial theft is answered by *Sango*, whose traditional punishment is death by lightning. The disproportion seems staggering. No human court would impose execution for petty theft.

Yet within *Ayélála* jurisprudence, different considerations apply that complicate this assessment:

³¹ OO Elechi, 'Doing Justice Without the State: The Afikpo (Ehugbo) Nigeria Model' (2006) 1 African Journal of Criminology and Justice Studies 1, 12.

³² OT Shemudara, 'Oath Taking in Administration of Justice and Assumption of Offices in Nigeria: An Illusion or Reality' (2024) 2(8) AAUA Journal of the Department of Jurisprudence and International Law 112, 119.

³³ Shemudara (n23)

³⁴ Shemudara (n 23) 61

³⁵ Shemudara (n23) 79

First, the offence is not only against the human victim. Theft, even of a needle, disrupts cosmic order. It offends not only the individual but the community and the spiritual forces that sustain communal life. The divinity's response addresses this multidimensional harm. *Ayélála's* sanctions were calibrated not to the material value of what was stolen but to the spiritual significance of the violation.³⁶

Second, and critically, the punishment serves corrective rather than purely retributive purposes. The researcher submits that *Ayélála* criminal justice system is not classical deterrence designed merely to discourage through threat. Nor is it simply retribution designed to visit equivalent harm upon the offender. Rather, it exhibits the correctional purpose of criminal punishment. It has its beauty encapsulated in its effectiveness: the preservation of social order achieved not through the infliction of injury, but through the threat of ultimate sanction combined with the opportunity for redemption.

Third, the divinity's punishment, though nominally uniform, is in practice graduated and conditional. The progression from sickness to death, with the intervening possibility of *lele*, means that the "sentence" is never final until the offender's own conduct renders it so. This is proportionality through temporal extension, the severity of ultimate outcome is tempered by the duration and conditions of the process leading to it.

Fourth, the disproportion communicates gravity while preserving mercy. By answering small wrongs with the threat of catastrophic sanctions, the divine realm signals that no offence is trivial in the cosmic balance; yet by providing the mechanism of *lele*, it ensures that the threat rarely needs to be fully executed. The message is prophylactic and corrective: better to suffer proportionate human justice than risk divine fury, yet divine fury itself offers pathways home.

A concrete scenario garnered and documented through fieldwork, a woman loses a needle, a small iron implement, perhaps her only one, but materially of negligible value. She suspects it was taken by someone in the compound but cannot prove who. The matter is brought to the elders. Human investigation fails. The community invokes *Ayélála*.

Days later, a young man in the compound falls ill with sickness of unknown cause. The community understands: *Ayélála* has begun the work of identification. The young man is visited by the priest; he is given opportunity for *lele*. If he confesses, makes restitution, and undergoes the purification ritual, the sickness lifts; he is discharged, the community is cleansed, relationships are restored.

If he denies, persists in concealment, the sickness progresses. Only then, after opportunities for repentance have been exhausted, does death supervene. By this point, the community's understanding has shifted: the death is not punishment for the theft alone, but for the compounded offence of theft and defiance of the divine order, and refusal of mercy.

By any human measure, the ultimate punishment remains severe. Yet within the framework of *Ayélála* justice, different considerations apply. The system is not merely for inflicting injury on any offender.³⁷ It exhibits the correctional purpose of criminal punishment. The preservation of social order is achieved the major pursuit of criminal punishment without necessarily diminishing the overall welfare of society through execution. The death that occurs is, in a sense, self-imposed: the refusal of mercy becomes its own sentence.

Fieldwork reveals that communities understood this logic precisely. They did not expect proportionality from the divinities in the English sense of graded offences. What they expected was accountability combined with opportunity, the certainty that wrongs would be addressed, that spiritual order would be maintained, and that the offender could, through acknowledgment, avert the ultimate sanction.³⁸

4.4 Multiple Conceptions of Justice in African Thought

The contrast between restorative proportionality for known offenders and the graduated divine sanction for unknown offenders reveals that African legal thought contains multiple, context-dependent conceptions of justice. This is not contradiction but sophistication different situations invoke different frameworks.

Where humans can act, they should act restoratively, aligning responses to repair harm. Where humans cannot act, the divine acts through mechanisms that combine severity with mercy. The two registers coexist, each with its own logic. The *Ayélála* system demonstrates that even the divine register, apparently most retributive, incorporates restorative elements through the institution of *lele*.

This insight has profound implications for comparative study. It is not enough to characterise African justice as restorative, nor to dismiss divine justice as merely retributive. One must account for the complex interplay of threat and mercy, of cosmic order and individual redemption that characterises the graduated sanctions of divinities like *Ayélála*.

³⁶ Shemudara (n 24) 63; Shemudara (n 21) 78; Shemudara (n 23) 122

³⁷ *ibid*

³⁸ *ibid*

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

The analysis reveals multiple divergences and convergences, there is issue of classification and uniformity under the English law. English law operates through elaborate classification of offences by gravity, with corresponding gradations of punishment. *Ayélála* jurisprudence operates through uniform ultimate sanction (death) differentiated by procedural opportunities for discharge (*lele*).

English justice is entirely human-administered. When offenders are unknown, the matter simply closes. African justice invokes divine agency precisely when human agency fails, but this divine agency operates through graduated processes that incorporate human response.

English law provides for parole early release based on good behaviour during incarceration but not for *allocutus* in the sense of discharge through confession after sentence. *Ayélála* provides the functional equivalent of *allocutus* (*lele*) as a central mechanism, but lacks the English system's graded sentencing tariffs or measure.

Under the English justice system, there is acceptance of fact or position that some wrongs will go unpunished. This is a limitation of human justice. African thought refuses this limitation, insisting that all wrongs must be addressed even if this requires supernatural intervention.

It must also be stated that despite these divergences, convergences still exist. It is among the findings that both systems value accountability. English law seeks to hold offenders accountable through human institutions. African thought insists on accountability even when human institutions fail, turning to the divine.

Again, both justice systems recognise corrective purposes. English law's rehabilitation focus and *Ayélála*'s *lele* institution both seek, in different ways, to restore the offender to community rather than merely punish.

The findings also reveal that both systems struggle with the problem of unknown offenders. English law accepts this as insoluble. African legal thought refuses acceptance, invoking the divine therefore, both recognise the problem; they differ in their response.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This comparative study has examined proportionality in English and African justice systems, with particular attention to the role of sacred divinities in African jurisprudence. It has revealed that African legal thought contains multiple conceptions of justice: restorative proportionality for known offenders, and a divine register for unknown offenders where human standards of proportionality do not directly apply.

However, detailed examination of the *Ayélála* divinity's criminal jurisprudence complicates simplistic narratives of "disproportionate" divine punishment. Unlike English law's classification of offences into categories of gravity with corresponding punishments, *Ayélála* threatens uniform ultimate sanction which is death for stealing as for murder. Yet this death is not spontaneous; it is gradual, beginning with sickness, and incorporates the institution of *lele* (*allocutus*) through which the accused may confess, repent, and be discharged.

The Yoruba proverb about the needle and the thunder god captures an apparent paradox: a petty theft answered with lethal sanction. Yet the reality of *Ayélála* jurisprudence suggests that even the thunder god offers mercy before the final strike. The system is not classical deterrence, nor mere retribution, but exhibits the correctional purpose of criminal punishment. It preserves social order, the major pursuit of criminal punishment without necessarily diminishing overall welfare through execution. Its beauty lies in its effectiveness: the combination of ultimate accountability with procedural opportunity for redemption.

English law, with its commitment to rational proportionality through classification and its acceptance of unsolved crimes, offers one response to the problem of wrongdoing. African thought, with its dual registers of restorative human justice and graduated divine sanction tempered by *lele*, offers another. Neither is complete. Comparative study reveals not which is superior but how each illuminates the other's assumptions and limitations.

6.1 Recommendations

In view of the foregoing it is recommended that sentencing guidelines in jurisdictions influenced by English law should explicitly recognise restorative outcomes as potentially proportional responses for appropriate offences. Courts should be empowered to order restitution, reconciliation processes, or community repair where these adequately address harm caused.

In addition to above, it is recommended that legal frameworks should acknowledge the legitimate communal need for accountability even when offenders cannot be identified. While supernatural invocation is unavailable to secular systems, community healing rituals, symbolic reparations, and public acknowledgments of wrongdoing can address some of the same needs. These should incorporate opportunities for "secular *lele*" formal mechanisms for acknowledgment and discharge that parallel the corrective function of divine *allocutus*.

Third, comparative legal scholarship must attend to the full complexity of African jurisprudence, including the graduated nature of divine sanctions and institutions like *lele*. Characterising African justice simply as "restorative" or divine justice as "disproportionate" misses the crucial dimensions revealed in careful ethnographic study.

Fourth, further research should examine how communities that traditionally invoked divine sanctions now address unknown offenders in contexts where supernatural frameworks have weakened. What substitutes for *lele* have emerged? How is the

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correctional purpose preserved when divine threat is no longer credible? This research should inform policy responses to the "justice gap" created by the decline of traditional mechanisms without adequate state replacement.

Again, legal education in Africa should engage seriously with indigenous jurisprudence, including its apparent paradoxes and its sophisticated procedural mechanisms. The needle and the thunder god, properly understood, is not a primitive confusion but a meditation on the limits of human justice, the values that exceed proportionality, and the mercy that tempers severity.

Finally, policymakers engaged in law reform in African jurisdictions should recognise that the *Ayelála* justice system, despite apparent severity, serves correctional purposes that secular systems struggle to replicate. Reform should seek to preserve the function of *lele*, the opportunity for acknowledgment and discharge within human rights-compliant frameworks, rather than merely abolishing traditional mechanisms without adequate substitutes.

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